

Supplementary materials

Photoreforming of PET and PLA microplastics for sustainable hydrogen production using TiO_2 and $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ photocatalysts

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Figure 1S Number of research and review articles on microplastics in time. Data were taken from Web of Science using a topic “microplastics” (1985-2024).

Figure 2S. The batch reactor used for photocatalytic measurements with 254 nm pen-ray lamp

1. Characterization of TiO₂ and g-C₃N₄ photocatalysts before photoreforming

UV-VIS diffusion reflectance spectra in the range of 220–1400 nm were recorded by a spectrophotometer Shimadzu UV-2600 with an integrated sphere attachment ISR-2600Plus at room temperature.

The specific surface area of each nanomaterial was measured by a device SORPTOMATIC 1990 series. SSA was determined by the analysis of N₂ adsorption isotherm at -196 °C by means of the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method.

Transmission electron microscopy was performed with a JEOL 2100 microscope with a LaB6 electron gun. The accelerating voltage of 200 kV was applied. Micrographs were taken by a camera Tengra (EMSIS). For the TEM analysis the samples were prepared by dispersion in ethanol and then were sonicated for 5 minutes. One drop of this solution was placed on a copper grid with a holey carbon film and dried at room temperature.

The mean size of TiO₂ particles was determined at 21 nm and its specific surface area (BET) was determined at 50 m² g⁻¹. The specific surface area (BET) of g-C₃N₄ was 140 m² g⁻¹

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Table 1S Band-gap energies (E_b) of TiO_2 and $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$

Photocatalysts	E_b (eV) indirect transition	E_b (eV) direct transition
TiO_2	3.22	3.73
$\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$	2.68	3.00

Note: The band-gap energies were determined according to Tauc's method.

Table 2S Selected characteristics of TiO_2 photocatalyst

Sample	P25
S_{BET} ($\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$)	50
Average diameter (nm)	26
TiO_2 content (wt. %)	99.4
Anatase (wt. %)	75
Rutile (wt. %)	25

Note: The data were provided by the manufacturer.

Figure 3S Diffuse reflectance spectra of TiO_2 and $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ photocatalysts.

Figure 4S FTIR spectrum of g-C₃N₄.

Figure 5S XRD patterns of g-C₃N₄ The diffraction peaks (002) and (100) at about 27.7° 2θ and 13.0 ° 2θ, respectively.

Figure 6S TEM micrograph of TiO_2 .

Figure 7S TEM micrograph of g- C_3N_4 .

2. Thermodynamic analysis

The combustion reactions of PET and PLA can be described by reactions

The enthalpies of these reactions can be calculated according to the Hess law

$$\Delta_r H_{298}^0 = \Delta H_{comb}^0 = \sum_i (\nu_i \Delta H_{f,i}^0)_{product} - \sum_i (\nu_i \Delta H_{f,i}^0)_{reactant} \quad (3\text{S})$$

The reaction entropies of the reaction (1) and (2) were calculated as

$$\Delta_r S_{298}^0 = \sum_i (\nu_i \Delta S_i^0)_{product} - \sum_i (\nu_i \Delta S_i^0)_{reactant} \quad (4\text{S})$$

Table 3S Standard enthalpies and entropies used for calculations

Substance	$\Delta H_{298,f}^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS_{298}^0 (kJ K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
H ₂ (g)	0	130.68
O ₂ (g)	0	205.15
H ₂ O (g)	-241.83	188.84
H ₂ O (l)	-285.83	69.95
CO ₂ (g)	-393.52	213.79
CO (g)	-110.53	197.55
CH ₄ (g)	-74.6	186.26

3. Experimental results

Figure 8S. HPLC/HRTMS analysis of PET after photocatalysis. (left) Reconstructed chromatograms at m/z 165.0193, (right) MS spectra collected at the retention time of terephthalic acid (RT: 4.54 and 4.50 min, respectively; c(TA)=2.25 mg/L).

Figure 9S Ratios of hydrogen yields evolved by photolysis in the water and NaOH suspensions of PET and PLA.

Figure 10S XRD patterns of TiO_2 (P25) before and after photocatalysis for 24 h.

Figure 11S. XPS spectra of Na 1s of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ under UV irradiation for 4 h in water (left) and NaOH suspensions (right).